

Editor in Chief

**Dr Adebayo Ola
AFOLARANMI**

Department of Religious
and Intercultural Studies,
Lead City University,
Ibadan, Nigeria

Editors

Assoc. Prof Adekunle

Olusola OTUNLA

Department of Mass
Communication and Media
Technology,
Lead City University,
Ibadan, Nigeria

Dr Michael

GBADEGESIN

Department of Languages
and Literature
Lead City University,
Ibadan, Nigeria

Associate Editors

Dr Emmanuel O.

MALOMO

ECWA Gospel Centre,
Kano, Nigeria

Rebecca Oluwatosin

BANJO

Department of Peace
Studies and Conflicts
Resolution, Ajayi Crowther
University, Oyo, Nigeria

Dr Emmanuel Selome

FASINU

Department of Political
Science, Wesley University,
Ondo, Nigeria

**Yoruba Experience on Health and
Healing: Diagnostic Methods on Chronic
Ailments, Treatments and Implications
for Modern Medical Practice**

Joshua Sijuade OGUNLADE

ogunladesijuade88@gmail.com, +2348039720420,
+2348029500119

Abstract

This article focuses on the spiritualities concerning health and healing in Africa. It examines methods for discerning chronic ailments, treatments, and implications for biomedical practice, in the acceptance of technology vis-à-vis traditional medical practices. Traditional medicine is cultural, a natural first aid, and transgenerational; hence, the existence, survival, practice, and application of indigenous methods for discerning chronic ailments and their treatment. Previous work on the subject matter focused on biomedicine, beliefs about traditional medicine, first-aid medicines, and the integration of African traditional medicine. For instance, many scholars have previously written that to find out the root cause of ailments is the panacea to curative medication, in that African Traditional medicine is tied to the culture of “homoeopathy”- using the like to cure the like. Unlike modern medical practice, called “allopathy,” where curing symptoms is the sole goal, people nowadays have been combining the two healing processes. As expository as the works of these scholars are, none has properly discussed the African Traditional Medical methods for diagnosing chronic ailments, their treatments, and implications for modern medicine. The findings of this study showed that biomedical practitioners, subject-matter experts in discerning chronic ailments, treatments, and implications, help

prevent incorrect prescriptions and poor treatments, and prevent prolonged illness, stress, wasteful spending, stigma, and unwanted death. Implicitly, the traditional medication for chronic ailments is neither complementary nor aloof but an integral part of a wholesome medication regimen, enhancing modern medical practice.

Keywords: Religion, Ailments, Diagnostic, Chronic, Biomedicine.

Introduction

In Africa, culture, traditions, rituals, and rites play a tremendous role in our holistic well-being, backed by indigenous technology for diagnostic procedures. Over the past two decades, considerable interest has been revived in the study and use of traditional medicine across different cultural settings. As a result, different countries have sought cooperation from the WHO (World Health Organisation) to identify and use traditional medicine within their respective national healthcare systems. The World Health Organisation encourages and supports countries in identifying, providing, and practising safe and effective traditional remedies for use in the public health sector. Owing to the definition of health by the World Health Organization (WHO), it is the state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity. Whereas, in 1984, it is the extent to which an individual or group can achieve goals or targets and satisfy needs to change, cope and interact with the environment. However, no one can rule out the spiritual aspect of life in relation to healthcare; therefore, Abilawon (2024) defined it as the state of complete physical, mental, social, and spiritual well-being of an individual or a community at large. In the light of the above, the various resolution passed by the world health organization indicates that; most of the world's population depends on traditional medicine for primary healthcare, the work force represented by the practitioners of the traditional medicine is a potential important human resource for the delivery of healthcare and medicinal plants are of great benefit to the health of individuals and communities. Nevertheless, we shall explore the significant role in discerning chronic ailments, treating them, and analysing the implications for modern medical practice.

Previous research on African Traditional Religion and chronic ailments, treatment, and implications for modern medical practice has focused on infectious diseases and treatment, biomedicine, first-aid medication, beliefs about traditional medicines, and traditional medical analysis. It is, for

instance, arguable that discerning and disarming chronic ailments is a crucial healthcare management procedure. Moreover, we believe that discerning chronic ailments in Africa, their treatment, and their implications for modern medical practice are eye-openers and a contemporary measure for combating current health issues. However, there is a line of demarcation between the duo. Numerous researchers, in their opinion, aver that the field of medicine is widely liberal. However, as expository as the work of these scholars is, none has properly discussed the African Traditional Religion methods for discerning chronic ailments, their treatment, and their implications for modern medical practice; this is the vacuum this study seeks to fill.

As we know that, medicine means a term for a set of social practices by which man seeks to direct and control wide range of natural phenomenon viz; those especially affecting man himself, which so influence his behaviour as to unfit him for the normal accomplishment of his physical, social and spiritual functions, phenomena which lower his vitality and tend towards death (Hutton, 1988). However, among the challenges to the methods of discerning chronic ailments, treatment, and implications for modern medical practice is that of appreciation, integration and application because of cultural degradation coupled with civilisation, whereas the subject matter would be serving as the firsthand source of primary healthcare, first-aid and curative treatment of chronic ailments. In the short and long run, educational institutions, government agencies, herbalists, and modern biomedical practitioners stand to benefit immensely from this research work.

Sequel to the above subject matter, the researcher aims and objects to;

1. Pinpoint relative diagnostic methods in African traditional medicine
2. Find out the root causes of sickness in Africa
3. Reveal African traditional medicine's implications on bio-medicine

The subject of sickness and medicine is complex and controversial. The researcher is curious to ask the following pertinent questions;

1. What are possible causes of ailments in Africa?
2. What are home or indigenous treatment/remedies?
3. What implications does it have on bio-medicine?

Methodology

This research combined quantitative textual analysis and qualitative field research to examine health and healing procedures from both the indigenous and diasporic African traditional medicine.

Theoretical Framework

This research is grounded in “traditional religion adaptation theory” and “communal survival strategy theory,” which help explain how people adjust their cultural and religious practices across various communities. Traditional Religious Adaptation theory explains how religious traditions modified their structures, practices, or resilience to survive despite certain ailments, as in the case study of the 1945 Ilesa disease outbreak. Meanwhile, communal survival strategy theory is associated with indigenous and native medicine and technology, which use available resources to solve problems by drawing on transgenerational knowledge.

Literature Review

Beaver et al. (1982), authorities in this field, found in their work among herbalists that traditional medicine is in the realm of religion, possibly with some empirical evidence of magic. The ethno-medicine of any human group in Africa comprises both metaphysical and natural elements, such that one cannot understand the ethno-medicine of the tradition separately from the overall culture within which it is derived and applied. Health disorders are believed to be caused by evil spiritual forces like witches, demons, wizards, sorcerers, who are enemies of their host or as an agent of punishment for evil done in the past. This implies that traditional medicine can be used for the good of humanity, as well as for disciplinary measures against immoral persons. However, this explanation may not always hold; ailments can also have natural causes. It seems to be an alternative way of explaining biological malfunction in the body due to insufficient knowledge of the dynamics of human chemistry. For instance, it might be claimed that evil ones are sucking the blood of a person losing weight as a result of malnutrition. Through research, we understand better that health disorders may be due to certain unhygienic and irrelevant practices. Despite this awareness, in modern times, it is still believed that evil forces can cause the body of their victim to malfunction. While the nature of western medication is allopathic, African medicine and herbs are heteropathy in nature thereby

diagnoses ailments holistically in order to know, cure and or prevent both the root and immediate cause of ailments: In African Traditional Religion, ailments especially, the ones with chronic conditions are often seen as disruption in the balance between the physical, spiritual, and communal realms. These chronic ailments are slower to respond to treatments, with significant damage to the victims, to the extent of shortening life expectancy. Factors known to contribute to these types of ailments include poor lifestyle, malnutrition, and lack of physical exercise. Information from global records shows that chronic ailments are the leading cause of death and disability commonly found among the lower- and middle-class people of the economy. Beyond the above, social, economic, and environmental factors can also influence the prevalence and management of chronic conditions, which have a burdensome economic impact due to their long-term nature and often noncurable status. Traditional medicine is directly connected with culture and religion. No aspect of African life is devoid of its cultural practices and religious beliefs. In African understanding, existence is a religious phenomenon; man is a religious being living in a religious universe. The application of traditional medicine focuses on eliminating the root cause of a disease. An herbalist can first consult the gods through an oracle to determine the cause of the disease and its treatment. Kola Abimbola refers to biomedicine as allopathic medicine, and to traditional medicine as homeopathic medicine. He writes that "...allopathic medicine is preoccupied with getting rid of the symptoms, meanwhile, homeopathic medicine is more concerned with identifying the causes of the illness and disease in an effort to restore holistic balance in the biological system" Traditionally, (E. O. Babalola 2003) writes that an herb from first-hand extraction does not just restore physical stability but also spiritual wholeness especially when combined with certain incantations. This shows that in Africa, medicine is a homegrown solution for Africans due to the inaccessibility of orthodox medicine. Since life is all about existence and survival, the first line of treatment for people with one illness or another is the use of herbal medicines at home. Hence, traditional medicine is divided into curative and preventive types.

Curative medicine is the treatment and therapies administered to a patient with the intent to cure the patient's ailing problems. Generally, it involves herbs, roots, leaves, seeds, salt, bark, and a host of other substances. Instances abound of these types of curative medicine and the ailment to

which they are applied. For instance, to treat cough (tuberculosis), Kola Abimbola (2006), another African scholar, explains that the ingredients are sugar-cane cut into pieces, soft banana, and Shea butter. In contrast, victims of sickness, such as thunderbolt, will require certain rites and rituals before adequate restoration. He adds that when these things are boiled in water, we obtain a kind of syrup that, when applied constantly, would give the patient some relief and eventually a cure. Ogundele (2017) agreed with Kola, explaining that high blood pressure can be cured by grinding or pounding five to ten large onions, with an equal proportion of garlic and ginger. All of these are placed inside a half-litre of honey in a container. This mixture is to be taken twice daily. He adds that another option is to squeeze fresh bitter leaves into a container with a small amount of water, then drink the mixture twice daily. However, Lucas (S.O., 2001) opined that preventive medicine is used as a shield against future attacks. To protect against attacks from enemies and wicked ones, people can wear traditional charms and amulets around their waists; some wear them as rings on their fingers. It can be buried as part of a house's foundation or hung at the entrances of people's houses. All of these are done to ward off evil and prevent the evil ones' activities.

There have been undeniable changes in the lives of Africans. According to Mbiti (1975), Christianity, Islam, education, and the dawn of orthodox medical doctors have tampered with the wholeness of Africa's traditional medicine. Despite the changes, belief in traditional medicine remains pervasive. Traditional medicine is still patronised by many people in rural and urban areas because of its accessibility and enduring cultural and psychological values. African consult herbalists who use various forms of divination to identify root causes and applicable herbs and traditional medicines. It now comes in pills; there are established modern medicine firms where drugs are processed with African plants and herbs. Herbal soaps, herbal mouthwash, and herbal drugs are advertised in print and mass media. Local midwives still handle childbirth at a higher rate, providing evidence that people in modern times still accept traditional medicine.

According to Jegede (2010), this acceptance is due to the lower cost of traditional medicines compared with orthodox medicines, which are expensive because of modern science and technology. Furthermore, since traditional medicine is homemade and readily available, it can be prepared

with or without supervision if one knows the required ingredients and method of preparation. The monopoly on the cure of certain diseases, such as piles, with orthodox medicine has now been broken. Curing piles on African land can be successful by grinding a leaf called “*efirin*” and mixing it with lime for the patient to lick. When discussing spiritual and religious healing, foreigners often equate the spiritual dimensions of traditional medicine with the prevailing religion. However, during the 1922-1955 period, there were increasingly clear distinctions between traditional medicine and religion. For the purposes of understanding the spiritual aspects of traditional healing and the ways religion and healing impacted each other, research on this subject matter discovered that; traditional religion circa 1922; spirituality and healing in Africa, components of traditional religion relative to healing, and the divinities that relate to traditional healing, e.g. Ifa, Osayin, Saponna, Osun, Obatala, Ogun, Yemoja, and Sango have great impact on health maintenance of Africans (Jegede, 2010). Furthermore, the relationship between Islam, Christianity, and traditional medicine is analysed here. In this article, it becomes apparent that the flexibility of traditional medicine is useful at a spiritual level, regardless of the practitioner's or patient's religion. Another reason for the resiliency of traditional medicine between 1922 and 1955 is its availability and accessibility. For instance, Traditional Religion Circa 1922 at Ife, in relation to the rest of Africa, was known as the original kingdom of the Yoruba people because Oduduwa settled there. Oduduwa was the original ancestor and first king of the Yoruba people. Descendants of Oduduwa were noted as the identifying marker of a Yoruba person, at times more so than speaking a Yoruba dialect. Certain Nigerian Yoruba groups did not claim Oduduwa, yet many Dahomeans claimed to have descended from Oduduwa. The Yoruba nationalist leader Obafemi Awolowo championed the relationship to Oduduwa as the definition of "Yoruba" in 1948 and secured international recognition of this ideology. However, it had been common among the Yoruba beforehand.

To buttress the work of Jegede, we agree with him that Oduduwa was regarded as the Yoruba's progenitor among most local kingdoms. The significance of Oduduwa as the symbolic representative of the Yoruba lies in how deeply Yoruba kingdoms and societies were anchored in indigenous religion(s). Modupe Opeola's alternative theory to describe Yoruba origins asserts that it was actually "odu" that united the Yoruba people.

Additionally, he notes that Odu and Oduduwa were "the same." There is additional evidence to support this theory because Oduduwa translates as 'Odu exists. The Odu were the consistently evolving segment within the Ifa corpus. The Odu were known as the Yoruba's cultural, philosophical, and historical archives. The existence of Odu may be the revolution that Oduduwa, as a historical character, represents. Oduduwa was the description of the establishment of a new dynasty c. 1000 CE, in which the Ifa corpus guided the Yoruba kingdoms. This concept exemplifies how intricately woven traditional religion and secular life were, examining connections between traditional medicine and religion. During this colonial period, both Christians and colonialists sought to remove many traditional religious and spiritual connotations from the Yoruba culture, e.g., stories of origin. Samuel Johnson inscribed the legacy of Oduduwa, without reference to Odu, in his legendary text.

Recently, a colonial report of 1930 notes that there was, at one time, a set of herbalists specially licensed by the king; they were remarkable for their skill in secret poisons, which were at the king's service when required, but failure to produce a fatal effect meant death to themselves. The knowledge of poisons is still considerable. The king's "herbalists" were priests of Ifa. The Ifa corpus was a common feature of traditional religion, regardless of whether the kingdom paid allegiance to 'Oduduwa' and despite the worship of other orisa (divinities) (Read, 1990). The CMS missionaries encountered babalawos across Africa prior to colonial rule. They found unity among religion, society and government. The king or oba, as the custodian of local divinities, made offerings on behalf of the public at shrines because these were the places "where the presence of a spirit is more eminent." Ancestor and divinity spirits then blessed towns with peace, food, children, etc.

Communal festivals, for instance, had multiple purposes, including purifying the town so that citizens would have good health and long lives. During the colonial period (1922-1955), festivals lasted for days, weeks, and even months. The majority of scholars in Africa believe that this world in which men are placed was created by God, the Supreme Deity, who also created man. The idea of God as the creator of both the world and man finds numerous expressions in their sayings, myths, folktales, and other vehicles of oral tradition, so there can be no doubt that this testimony is a firmly established belief and of captivating imponderability for the whole worldview of the Yoruba. Idowu has already given us the picture of how this

world was created long ago by Olodumare, the Supreme Being, who instructed Orisanla, the arch-divinity, to perform the creative functions. The African people have practised medicine for a very long time, with no clear date of origin, and it is still practised today. It is as old as the traditional religion. We have folklore, stories and oral traditions (Odu Corpus) as means of establishing the antiquity of medical practices. According to Ogunlade (2025), certain divinities feature prominently in the practice of medicine, and their names appear so often in incantations. In his work, Dopamu mentions the following divinities: Ifa, Orisanla, Obatala, Esu, Osonyin, Aja, Arori Songo, and Ogun. Dopamu presents the Africans' beliefs about these divinities and their relationship to medicine, since one cannot separate people from their respective cultures as identity markers. Culture, which is the totality of the ways of life of a people, encompasses the totality of people's beliefs and practices. There are so many cultures in the world, each marked by its distinct qualities. For instance, we have Iranian, Asian, and Russian cultures. In Africa, Nigeria, for instance, also have Yoruba culture, Berom culture, Efik culture, etc. One prominent aspect of these African cultures is homoeopathic medical culture, which is the concern of this paper.

One specific feature of culture is its originality. In this respect, for a way of life of a particular people to be regarded as a culture, it must be devoid of influx from people not of their culture. Second, African culture is situated in the metaphysical belief in supernatural beings (Abilawon, 2009), avers that Olodumare, the Orisas, and the *oku orun*. This marks their belief in two planes of existence, Orun and Aye, Aye (and everything therein, including the human body and soul) is believed to be created by Olodumare and the Orisas who reside in Orun. This informs their belief that the souls of the dead return to Orun, where they came from, to continue living there. However, the requirement is that these souls must have fulfilled their mission in Aye before they are admitted to Orun to continue living as ancestors. The best that could be called for is systematic development in some aspects of the culture. One of the covert aspects of African culture is to ensure the good health and wellbeing of the people. Good health includes the provision of healing from various kinds of illness and disease. Correspondingly, Ghadegesin (2004) writes, "is sought for in all the nations of the world and is usually for various kinds of diseases and sicknesses". There are so many ways different cultures approach the issue of ensuring

people's healing and good health. Some cultures focus extensively on the physical wellbeing of people alone. This is achieved by providing a curative process for physical diseases and ailments. It is also a characteristic of Western medicine. African culture not only heals physical ailments but also supports the patient's spiritual well-being. This is what is referred to as holistic healing. This ultimately distinguishes African traditional healing from other modes of healing. To achieve this, African herbalists use herbal medicine and also include incantation and invocation of spirits to achieve all-around healing. This background thus shows the connection of African traditional medicine with their cultural belief in the supernatural.

Gbadegesin (2004), in his opinion, posits that in our world of today, curiosity to unravel subtle and non-obvious matters presupposes due attentions, which brought about the subject matter of this article, ailments are not just treated without due investigations referred to as diagnosis and examination by the modern medical practitioners (Lucas, 2021). To determine the cause or causes of any chronic ailments, herbalists would ask patients questions and make spiritual inquiries by consulting mediums to reach out to ancestral spirits and others. Though it is multifaceted in nature, as deduced above, it aims to gain insight into present predicaments to predict the future, as a means of understanding the hidden forces behind a course. The methods in use range from magic conjuration, trancing, Ifa corporation, astronomical investigation, palm reading, scrying, bird message, and the like. The sacred objects used in the above methods include, but are not limited to, cowries, bones, kola nuts, snail shells, sand, guards, oracle, calabash, water, stones, and many more. The other aspect of divination is the revealed interpretation of outcomes, such as sign/symbol/omen reading. Usually, omens reveal the underlying causes and actions against chronic ailments. Therefore, divination serves functions such as uncovering hidden phenomena, providing divine understanding (Gbadegesin, 2004), and offering solutions that lead to magical rituals for the alleviation, manipulation, and protection of victims. In African Traditional Religion, the world is viewed as a dynamic interplay of visible and invisible entities converging at a point of compromise, providing opportunities for human activities and efforts for survival. This arises from the interconnectedness of realms for spiritual guidance, wisdom, balance, ethos, and values. However, certain elements inform discernment, among which perception and understanding, judgement and evaluation, distinction and analysis,

wisdom and insight are not far-fetched. Among the so-called chronic diseases are: thunderbolt (magun), spiritual attacks, hypnotism, asthma, an ailment of the lungs in which there is “short-air-breath”. It refers to the closure or inflammation of the respiratory airways, leading to gasping, collapse, and, if left untreated, eventual death. Another one is infertility- the malfunctioning of the reproductive system of a victim ranging from erectile dysfunctional, low sperm count, damaged womb/ blockage, cervical abnormalities, arthritis is another disease known with abnormal swollen on the body, pains, deformities, neck stiffness, bump growth and so on while epilepsy relates to asthma, characterized by; a complete seizure of breath, saliva foaming, unstable body, unconsciousness and many more. Worth noting are mental ailments characterised by sad feelings, confusion, excessive fear and worry, disorderliness, unwarranted violence, abnormal display and many more. Diabetes is a disease referred to as high blood sugar affecting a larger number of African populations. Leprosy, a subtle illness that separates loved ones, is a skin condition that can lead to the loss of fingers and toes, as well as other deformities. Cancer is not the only ailment in which body cells grow out of control, thereby leading to death. Obesity, an excessive fatness arising from overfeeding, lack of exercise, consequences of bad rituals or magic, is another sickness, as is Parkinson’s ailment, which is a low body system performance.

Findings

The concept of health and healing, especially in Yoruba communities in Africa, is a phenomenon that requires discernment, otherwise known as diagnosis. They involve a series of medical investigations which entail divination, consultation and a community cultural support system. This research indicates that cultural engagement and spiritual activities are a potent weapon against sicknesses in Africa. Additionally, since Africans are connected to ancestral spirits, the practice of traditional healing processes and methods is important. Integrating epidemiological data from Africa, cultural realities, and biomedical perspectives demonstrates that a holistic healthcare system goes beyond adoption or adaptation to encompass the most effective medical services.

Conclusion

Obtaining from the above, African Traditional medicine offers valuable insights into discerning underlying spiritual factors and multi-facet root causes to treating various class of chronic sicknesses devoid of bias as well as providing a template for bio-medical practice by understanding its appropriate approaches to health and healing procedures through which bio-medication can seek to develop a more robust, culturally-sensitive, wholistic and patient-centered healthcare models, particularly in diaspora context, since variety is option centered. The beauty of the market thereby removes the inferiority complex arising from the stigmatisation of the use of traditional medications. Medication among the Yoruba and biomedication may be closely related in terms of lexicon, but they are far different from one another. The exposition above has shown that activities and processes involved in the traditional health and healing practices among the Yorubas are holistic rather than allopathic, as in the biomedical process, which treats symptoms; the designations are clearly different. The traditional medical art is objective, using natural herbs, divinations, powers, and a community support system. Bio-medication is characterised by subjectivity in using synthetic drugs, in which the compositions of medicines are readily distorted and highly imbued in the psyche of the patients. This explains why the Yorubas believe that the root cause of ailments may go beyond physical but spiritual, which the patients under healthcare might not know or be aware of, for instance, witchcraft or sorcery. The issue here is that every herbalist knows and uses what he/she thinks could be used to carry out healing for these kinds of patients, the art of which could be sorcery or divination, as presented above.

Recommendations

1. Cultural preservation: African traditional medicine is cultural and should therefore be more preserved by the traditional institutions.
2. Further field research: future studies should incorporate more in-depth interviews on ethnomedicine.
3. Academic documentation: scholars should undertake more detailed research on African ailments, diagnostic methods such as divination.
4. Acknowledging medical pluralism: the community support system should promote combination medications to cure sickness.

5. Research on herbal knowledge: traditional medical remedies should be made public.
6. Integrative collaboration: both traditional herbalists and biomedical practitioners should form a formidable medical synergy.
7. Initiate and promote positive health partnership: there should be no isolation, stigmatisation of different medications
8. Developing an effective feedback system: there should be a reporting system which provides a basis for patronage
9. Drug and substance control agencies, such as NAFDAC and NDLEA, should monitor medical activities.
10. Medical awareness and constant training: medical field officers should receive constant training and re-training.

References

- Abilawon, S. (2009). Relevance of Yoruba Magic and Medicine for Contemporary Nigerian Society. (unpublished), 24.
- Abimbola, W. *Yoruba Culture, a Philosophical Account, United Kingdom*. Iroko Academic Publisher, 28.
- Babalola, E. O. (2003). The Relevance of Herbal Medicine to the Practice of African Traditional Religion, Islam and Christianity in EPHA. *Ekpoma Journal Religious Studies*, 103-110
- Beaver, R. P. et al. (1982). *The World's Religion Handbook*. Lion Publishing Plc.
- Gbadegesin, E. O. (2004). Revitalisation of African Healing in a Global Context. In Sola Akinrinade et al. *Locating the Global in the Global Voices on a Globalised Nigeria*. Faculty of Arts, OAU, Ile-Ife, Nigeria.
- Hutton, W. (1988). *A Sociological Study*. Stanford University Press.
- Jegede, C.O., (2010). Incantation and Herbal Cures in Ifa Divination. African Association for the Study of Religion, Ibadan. 14–15.
- Jegede. C. O. (2010). Incantation, Mid Herbal Cures in Ifa Divination. *African Association for the Study of Religion*, Ibadan 14-15
- Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English (African Edition), 1981. Longman Group Limited, 1129.
- Lucas, S.O. (2001). Witchcraft in: The Introduction, Background to Medical Practice in Nigeria. University of Ibadan, Institute of African Studies, Occasional Publication No. 125, 46.
- Mbiti, J.S. (1975). *Introduction to African Religion*. Heinemann.
- Read, C. (1990). *The Origin of Man and His Superstitions*. Cambridge University Press.